

IMPLEMENTATION OF TOURISM VILLAGES DEVELOPMENT COLLABORATION POLICY IN BINTAN REGENCY RIAU ISLAND PROVINCE - INDONESIA

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Abstract

This research was conducted to determine the implementation of the Collaborative Tourism Village Development Policy in Bintan Regency, Riau Islands Province. Tourism has experienced very rapid development so that the demand for various tourist objects and destinations is increasingly high, the presence of tourist villages is one answer to this need. The role of government and related stakeholders is becoming increasingly important in collaborating to respond to these developments. The formulation of the problem in this research is as follows: 1. How is the Implementation of the Collaborative Tourism Village Development Policy in Bintan Regency, Riau Islands Province?, 2. Why is the Implementation of the Collaborative Tourism Village Development Policy in Bintan Regency, Riau Islands Province not yet running effectively?, 3. What is the effective collaboration model in developing tourist villages between Tourism Village Managers and Third Parties? This research was designed descriptive - qualitative. to see the Implementation of Bintan Regent Regulation Policy No. 31 of 2022 concerning villages and tourist villages, researchers used Ryan Nugroho's Policy Implementation Theory (2004:159) and Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough's (2012) Collaboration Theory. This research was conducted in the tourist village of Bintan Regency, Riau Islands Province The conclusions of this research are: 1. Implementation of collaborative policies for developing tourist villages in Bintan Regency has not been implemented effectively. 2. Implementation of collaborative policies for developing tourist villages in Bintan district has not been carried out/implemented effectively due to passive elements of collaboration (not proactive). Researchers have designed/constructed an effective collaboration model in developing tourist villages. The model is “**POROS 1X-5Y in 5W-1H MODEL**”. Overall, the results of this research fully support/accept the three research hypotheses.

Keywords: Implementation, Policy, Collaboration, Government, Tourism, Tourism Village.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the country's main sources of foreign exchange after oil and gas, coal and palm oil. Currently the tourism sector is the sector most affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, however this situation does not change the important fact that apart from being able to contribute to national economic growth it also has an influence on regional and village economic growth. The main focus of tourism development is to build an area that becomes a tourist destination by relying on and optimizing the potential for the beauty of sustainable natural resources. Tourist destinations that rely on the beauty of natural resources include coastal areas, mountainous areas, lakes and islands

Figure 1.2: Bintan Has Strategic Linkages with Singapore as the Regional HUB2

Source: Bintan Regency RIPPARDA Document, 2014

Bintan Regency has a strategic position towards Singapore as a tourism hub, including:

- 1) There are around 1 million people from Singapore every year visiting the Riau Islands region, of which around 15% visit Bintan.
- 2) In 2012, Singapore was visited by almost 15 million international tourists.
- 3) Relatively similar market segments.
- 4) Accessible (short distance) 45 minutes by Fast Ferry.
- 5) Singapore expatriates who have above average income.
- 6) Bintan is expected to be a complementarity to Singapore, and not a competitor and Singapore needs the expansion of new tourism spaces and variations in tourist attractions.

From the geographical position and regional tourism of Bintan, the development of Bintan tourism both externally and internally is very prospective and strategic. The Bintan Regency Regional Government, in realizing the Bintan Gemilang Vision 2025 which focuses on the tourism sector, the tourism development side of the Bintan Regency Regional Government should pay attention to the opportunities and potential of the main sector, namely tourism, by directing sustainable maritime tourism development. Based on this Vision, it is clear that the achievement of this vision has been stated in the first mission and is important related to maritime optimization in the tourism sector, namely: Developing and optimizing maritime and tourism potential in a sustainable manner as a supporting capacity and leverage for regional development. Therefore, it is natural that Bintan Regency, which has 98% of its largest area is sea with 2% land, should start looking at developing tourism based on the maritime sector. It is very objective and rational in developing the Bintan Regency tourism sector to be developed in line with the Central Government's vision which wants to make Indonesia a World Maritime Axis. In line with central government policy, it emphasizes that developing marine tourism

potential has strategic significance in developing maritime culture, multi-sector businesses, regional economy, and strengthening community participation. This is added to the fact that marine tourism is one of the strategic and priority superior programs. The existence of tourist villages in the journey of tourism development in the country is so important and strategic with tourist villages being able to color a more dynamic variety of destinations in a tourism area, so that tourism is not always trapped in the development trend of mass tourism. Through tourist villages, tourism proves its support for the spirit of tourism as an absorber of rural sector workers, as a generator of utilization, development and regional economic growth, and as a tool for alleviating poverty.

Obstacles and challenges for tourist villages in their journey can be seen that there is limited vision or perception, clear attitudes and orientation of the community regarding tourism, low interest and awareness of the community, low capacity of human resources, the existence of cultural barriers, and frequent coercion. And lying to tourists. The enactment of Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages has created hope and optimized the development of new potential for villages. One of these hopes is that the village can develop its potential as a form of productive business to increase the prosperity of its citizens. The law mandates that every village in Indonesia in the future must have a Village-Owned Enterprise which has the mandate to run productive businesses, so that the village can prosper. Of course, the businesses that are developed are businesses that are rooted in the potential of each village. For villages that have great potential in the tourism sector, they can develop tourist villages. Bintan Regent Regulation No. 31 of 2022 concerning Villages and Tourism Villages in Bintan Regency. In Chapter VI, Development of Tourism Villages and Tourism Villages, Article 12 letters a-e mandates that the development of tourist villages be carried out by developing the infrastructure of Tourism Villages or Tourism Villages; Marketing of Tourism Villages or Tourism Villages; Strengthening the institutions of Tourism Villages or Tourism Villages; Partnership cooperation; and Developing the attractiveness of Tourism Villages or Tourism Villages but this has not yet been implemented in real terms in the field.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was designed with a descriptive - qualitative design type. Researchers will solely focus on describing the situation of the existing problem. The purpose of this design itself is to describe, explain and describe all situations, facts and conditions regarding existing problems accurately and systematically.

Population and Sample

To explore answers to research problems regarding the Implementation of the Collaborative Tourism Village Development Policy in Bintan Regency, Riau Islands Province, the population and sample were determined as follows:

Population: The population in this research is the Regional Government (Tourism Service), private companies in the District and/or Village areas (Tourism Villages), 7 Tourism Villages in Bintan Regency (Village Government and Village Consultative Body), tourism village

managers and community leaders, the Village Communication Forum Bintan Regency Tourism, SMEs and Tourism NGOs in Bintan Regency.

Sample: Sampling using purposive sampling or purposive sampling method, namely sampling by determining certain groups that have their own characteristics related to the research data. The sample in this study consisted of elements of the Regional Government (Tourism Service), private companies in the District and/or Village areas (Tourism Village), 7 Tourism Villages in Bintan Regency (Village Government and Village Consultative Body), tourism village managers and community leaders, Forum Communication of the Bintan Regency Tourism Village, MSMEs and Tourism NGOs in Bintan Regency.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Policy Implementation Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) In Collaborative Governance Emerson, Nabatchi dan Ballough (2012)

Figure 1: Flow/Stage1: Intervention Program-Ryan Nugroho (2004:159)

Description: Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 1: Intervention Program – Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) is influenced by three elements of collaborative governance Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

1) Flow/Stage 1: Intervention Program in System Context/Scope Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 1: Intervention Program - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that the Intervention Program does not exist/does not yet exist in the development of tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention program. Meanwhile, the collaborative governance element of Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012), namely the System Context/Scope element, consists of various stakeholders/elements that are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy objectives, but this scope has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention programs in implementing development policies tourist village in Bintan Regency.

2) Flow/Stage 1: Intervention Program in the Drivers Element

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 1: Intervention Program - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that the Intervention Program does not exist/does not yet exist in the development of tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention program. Meanwhile, the Drivers/Mover element - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) consists of various stakeholders/elements who are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy goals, however the existence of drivers/mover is very passive (not proactive) so that it has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention programs in implementing tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency.

3) Flow/Stage 1: Intervention Program in Collaboration Dynamics Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 1: Intervention Program - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that the Intervention Program does not exist/does not yet exist in the development of tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention program. Meanwhile, the Collaboration Dynamics element - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) does not exist/does not work. This is because the scope and existence of drivers/activators are still very passive (not proactive) and collaboration has not been developed so that the dynamics of collaboration do not occur. This of course has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention programs in implementing tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency.

2. Policy Implementation Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) In Elements of Collaborative Governance Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

Figure2. Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Project - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159)

Description: Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Project - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) is influenced by three elements of collaborative governance Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

1. Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Project in System Context/Scope Elements

From the research results, it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Program - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that the Intervention Project does not exist/does not yet exist in the development of tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention projects.

Meanwhile, the collaborative governance element of Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012), namely the System Context/Scope element, consists of various stakeholders/elements that are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy objectives, but this scope has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention projects in implementing village development policies. Tourism in Bintan Regency.

2. Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Project in Drivers Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Project - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that the Intervention Program does not exist/does not yet exist in the development of tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention projects.

Meanwhile, the Drivers/Mover element - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) consists of various stakeholders/elements who are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy goals, but the existence of drivers/movers is very passive (not proactive) so that it has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention projects in implementing tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency.

3. Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Project in Collaboration Dynamic Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 2: Intervention Project - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that the Intervention Program does not exist/does not yet exist in the development of tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention projects.

Meanwhile, the Collaboration Dynamics element - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) does not exist/does not work. This is because the scope and existence of drivers/activators are still very passive (not proactive) and collaboration has not been developed so that the dynamics of collaboration do not occur.

This of course has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention projects in implementing tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency.

3. Policy Implementation Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) In Elements of Collaborative Governance Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

Figure 3: Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Activities - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159)

Description: Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Activities - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) is influenced by three elements of collaborative governance Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

1) Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Activities in System Context/Scope Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Activities - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that Intervention Activities originating from and by relevant stakeholders/elements do not exist/do not yet exist. There have been activities carried out independently by the tourism office in developing tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention activities carried out jointly by related stakeholders/elements. Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough's (2012) collaborative governance element, namely the System Context/Scope element, consists of various stakeholders/elements that are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy objectives, but this scope has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention activities in implementing tourism village development policies. In Bintan Regency.

2) Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Activities in the Drivers Element

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Program - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that intervention activities originating from and by related stakeholders/elements do not exist/do not yet exist. There have been activities carried out independently by the tourism office in developing tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention activities carried out jointly by related stakeholders/elements. Drivers/Mover Elements - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

consist of various stakeholders/elements who are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy goals, however the existence of drivers/mover is very passive (not proactive) so that it has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention programs in implementing tourism village development policy in Bintan Regency. The Tourism Department has taken it as a driver so that several dians activities can be carried out, but this activity is purely the activity of the Tourism Department, the temporary manager of the tourist village is only a participant (Top Down activity).

3) Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Activities in Collaboration Dynamic Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 3: Intervention Activities - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that Intervention Activities originating from and by relevant stakeholders/elements do not exist/do not yet exist. There have been activities carried out independently by the tourism office in developing tourist villages in Bintan Regency. This policy was implemented without any intervention activities carried out jointly by related stakeholders/elements. Collaboration Dynamics elements - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) do not exist/do not work. This is because the scope and existence of drivers/activators are still very passive (not proactive) and collaboration has not been developed so that the dynamics of collaboration do not occur. This of course has not had an impact on the existence/creation of intervention programs in implementing tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency.

4. Policy Implementation Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) In Elements of Collaborative Governance Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

Figure 4: Flow/Stage 4: Beneficiary Communities - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159)

Description: Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 4: Community (Beneficiaries) - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) is influenced by three elements of collaborative governance Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

1) Flow/Stage 4: Beneficiary Community in System Context/Scope Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 4: Community (Beneficiaries) - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that there are communities (beneficiaries) but these communities have not received/felt the benefits of the policy in developing tourist villages in Bintan Regency.

This policy was implemented without any benefits received by the community. Meanwhile, the collaborative governance element of Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012), namely the System Context/Scope element, consists of various stakeholders/elements that are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy objectives, but this scope has not had an impact on the existence/creation of benefits for the beneficiary community in implementing it. Tourism village development policy in Bintan Regency.

2) Flow/Stage 4: Beneficiary Community in the Drivers Element

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 4: Community (Beneficiaries) - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that the Community exists, however the community has not felt/received the benefits from the implementation of the tourism village development policy in Bintan Regency.

This policy was implemented without any benefits for the beneficiary communities. Meanwhile, the Drivers/Mover element - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) consists of various stakeholders/elements who are very supportive in efforts to achieve policy goals, but the existence of drivers/mover is very passive (not proactive) so that it has not had an impact on the existence/creation of benefits for society beneficiaries in implementing tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency.

3) Flow/Stage 4: Beneficiary Community in Collaboration Dynamic Elements

From the research results it is known that Policy Implementation - Flow/Stage 4: Community (Beneficiaries) - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) that there are communities (beneficiaries) but these communities have not received/felt the benefits of the tourism village development policy in Bintan Regency.

This policy was implemented without any benefits for the beneficiary communities. Meanwhile, the Collaboration Dynamics element - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) does not exist/does not work. This is because the scope and existence of drivers/movers are still very passive (not proactive) and collaboration has not been developed so that the dynamics of collaboration do not occur.

This of course has not had an impact on the existence/creation of benefits for the beneficiary communities in implementing tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency.

From the analysis above as a whole it can be formulated into the following table;

Table 1: Policy Implementation - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159) in 3 elements of Collaborative Governance - Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012)

Policy Implementation - Ryan Nugroho (2004:159)	collaborative Governance - Emerson, Nabatchi dan Ballough (2012)		
	System Context Elements	Drivers Elements	Collaboration Dynamic Elements
Intervension Program	Yes (many) No	Yes (passive) No	Yes No.
Intervension Project	Yes (many) No	Yes (passive) No	No No.
Intervension Event	Yes (many) No	Yes (passive) No	No No.
Beneficiary Communities	Yes (many) Yes (not yet)	Yes (passive) Yes (not yet)	No Yes (not yet)

Source: Processed by Researcher, 2024

Figure 5: Collaboration Model for Tourism Villages Development Policy

PIVOT 1X- 5Y in 5W-1H MODEL

Caption:

Pivot X of Tourism Villages: are the main objects and subjects (Main Objects and Subjects); in tourist villages driven by tourism awareness groups (POKDARWIS) or Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDESA) which operate in the tourism sector in tourist villages.

Pivot Y1 Village Government: is the subject; namely the Village Government whose village has been designated as a tourist village in accordance with the applicable mechanisms and provisions.

Pivot Y2 Local Government: is the subject; namely the Regency/City Regional Government.

Pivot Y3 Private Company: is the subject; namely private companies that carry out business activities and their home base in tourist village areas, both business activities in the tourism sector and other business activities.

Pivot Y4 UMKM: is the subject; are local SMEs in tourist villages and SMEs in other village areas.

Pivot Y5 Tourism NGO: is the subject; is a local community social institution and community that operates in the tourism sector in the district area.

An explanation of the relationship pattern between the axes in the "**PIVOT 1X-5Y in 5W-IH MODEL**" collaboration for the development of tourist villages can be seen in the following table:

Table of X and Y connection patterns in

"PIVOT 1X-5Y In 5W-IH MODEL"

Pivot X	Pivot Y1	Pivot Y2	Pivot Y3	Pivot Y4	Pivot Y5
X – Y1	Y1 – X	Y2 – X	Y3 – X	Y4 – X	Y5 – X
X – Y2	Y1 – Y2	Y2 – Y1	Y3 – Y1	Y4 – Y1	Y5 – Y1
X – Y3	Y1 – Y3	Y2 – Y3	Y3 – Y2	Y4 – Y2	Y5 – Y2
X – Y4	Y1 – Y4	Y2 – Y4	Y3 – Y4	Y4 – Y3	Y5 – Y3
X – Y5	Y1 – Y5	Y2 – Y5	Y3 – Y5	Y4 – Y5	Y5 – Y4

Each X and Y pivot must have clear and measurable answers to questions 5W -1H which leads to the development and growth of tourist villages.

Tasks of each Pivot:

1. Have a clear and measurable answer to the question what/what is the issue?
2. Have a clear and measurable answer to the question why/why is it needed?
3. Have a clear and measurable answer to the question who/who is involved (1X - 5Y)?
4. Have a clear and measurable answer to the question where?
5. Have a clear and measurable answer to the question when?
6. Have clear and measurable answers to How questions?
7. Identify the current/existing conditions of tourist villages and the management of Pokdarwis/Bumdes as a whole using SWOT; Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats.
8. Conduct a SWOT Analysis

9. Make conclusions
10. Identify collaboration points with each axis
11. Coordinate and Collaborate proactively / subject with each axis

Tourism Village (pokdarwis/bumdesa), because apart from being an object to be developed, it is also a subject (Axis X) must be given legitimacy as a prime driver/main mover by axis Y and axis Y recognizes and respects the legitimacy that has been given. With this legitimacy, the X axis holds the main control in terms of initiation and coordination to ensure that each axis proactively collaborates in accordance with matters that have been mutually agreed upon between the X and Y axes as outlined in the form of a memorandum of understanding (MoU) document.

CONCLUSION

The Regent Regulation No. 31 of 2022 concerning Bintan Regency Tourism Villages and Villages, specifically for chapter VI article 12, letters d and e which are further explained in the fourth part, Cooperation article 16 paragraph (1) and paragraph (2) and article 17 letters a, b, c and d were not implemented because basically they have not been used as the main guidelines/references in developing tourist villages. The stakeholders do not understand it well and there is no proactive coordination and collaboration from the relevant stakeholders.

Collaboration by Emerson, Nabatchi and Ballough (2012) Collaborative Government Regime (CGR) consists of three elements: System Context, Drivers and Dynamic Collaboration. Dynamic Collaboration does not occur in the implementation of the Collaborative Policy for the Development of Tourist Villages in Bintan Regency. Stake holders have not been proactively involved in cooperation, coordination, let alone collaboration. Bupati Regulation no. 31 of 2022 concerning Bintan Regency Tourism Villages and Villages, specifically for chapter VI article 12, letters d and e which are further explained in the fourth part, Cooperation article 16 paragraph (1) and paragraph (2) and article 17 letters a, b, c and d have not been well coordinated, so that stakeholders have not been involved in proactive coordination and collaboration.

Based on the research problem formulation, it can be concluded that;

- 1) Implementation of collaborative tourism village development policies in Bintan Regency has not been implemented effectively.
- 2) Implementation of collaborative policies for developing tourist villages in Bintan district has not been carried out/implemented effectively due to passive elements of collaboration (not proactive). The flow/stages of Policy Implementation are not available and are not implemented. The flow/stages include intervention programs, intervention projects, intervention activities and communities (beneficiaries). Meanwhile, the elements of Collaborative Governance (system context/scope, Drivers/enablers and Collaborative dynamics/collaboration dynamics) are still very passive so they have not had a positive impact on the availability and implementation of the flow/stages of policy implementation.

- 3) Researchers have designed/constructed an effective collaboration model in developing tourist villages. The model is *"PIVOT 1X-5Y in 5W-1H MODEL"*.
- 4) Recommend to relevant stakeholders to use the collaborative policy implementation model for developing tourist villages "POROS 1X-5Y in 5W-1H MODEL" as a whole in developing tourist villages.

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